

Deliverable D6.1

Pilot (FR) Technical report and achieved results (1|2)

Deliverable report

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Disclaimer

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DIGIECOQUARRY project is fully concerned about the potential social risks that may arise as a consequence of the project's activities. For this reason, a dedicated Work Package (WP7 - Mechanisms for social acceptance & interaction with policymakers) is active since the beginning of the project identifying, analyzing and monitoring social risks in each of the project sites. Main social risks have been already analyzed and classified in deliverables 7.1 and 7.2, including also potential risks of DIGIECOQUARRY technologies' deployment beyond the end of the project. The identification and classification of social risks allow a close follow-up of the main potential negative impacts in society to avoid them throughout the whole project activities. Among potential social risks, the impact on the workforce is monitored with specific attention to ensure full adaptation of workers to new working technologies and processes and avoid job destruction.

To ensure a successful implementation of the developed technologies in the pilot sites, social risks identified in WP7 for each pilot have been carefully considered. WP6 also includes the assessment and monitoring of relevant KPIs, which will help reduce the risk of work accidents and minimize the environmental impact.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
WP	Work Package
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
BIM	Building Information Modeling
H&S	health and security
PC	Personal computer
AL3	feeder belt 3
C1, C2, C3	Screen sieve 1, 2, 3
K1	Cruscher 1
Cy3	Cycloning 3
Cv3	Tank 3
TR1, TR2, ...	"Rolled" conveyor belt 1, 2
TC1, TC2, ...	"crushed" conveyor belt

1 Pilot overview

Granulats VICAT's quarry represents 10,3% of quarries across Europe. It is specialized in raw materials recycling. It has a treatment plant where materials are inspected, washed, crushed, and stocked. The site has acquired a new washing system consisting of water tanks and pumps that allow us to recycle 90% of our water. Our main objective is to be able to predict and organize stock.

GRANULATS VICAT operates more than 40 quarries in France and 40 platforms. Very involved in the circular economy, 60 % of its sites among which the Fenouillet site participate to the recovery of construction and demolition wastes: recycling platforms or quarry's restoration made with external materials from job sites (earthworks, etc.). in terms of membership and clustering, the site in Fenouillet is an urban quarry. This a 46 000 M² place with neighbours such as Decathlon, Mc Donald, King Jouet, etc. This quarry has the particularity of not having any extraction site linked. It only works by recovering raw materials issued from local earthworks.

Here the focus will then be on optimizing production by establishing a preventive maintenance strategy. To do so, we must put in place tools that will help us prevent machines breakdowns, unexpected curative maintenance. In the scope of the project, it is expected to be installed or put in place:

- A BIM model for predictive maintenance.
- An electric mobile crusher.
- Environmental and energy consumption simulation platform.
- Weighting systems equipped with monitoring sensors linked to the SCADA.
- Artificial intelligence algorithms.
- A social acceptance strategy.

Figure 1: Overview of VICAT plant.

The plant’s priorities are mainly social acceptance and to improve treatment performances. More precisely, Vicat is concerned by KSA7.1 through a community engagement strategy for social acceptance in WP7, an innovative mobile crusher is expected to be tested on Vicat site piloted by METSO (WP3-KTA2.1) this will optimize the recovery of different types of materials coming from earthwork like recycled concrete while limiting noise emissions linked to the thermal engine as well as reducing fossil energy consumption. With WP4 partners, a BIM model is being worked on to improve predictive maintenance (KTA 4.1) and AI algorithms and cameras are being discussed to find their best usage (WP4 –KTA 4.2). Regarding Health, Safety & environmental management an online platform has been created and is going through updates (WP5 –KTA 5.1).

2 Implementation of technologies

For now, one technology has been implemented on site and more are being tested, studied or are in process.

Table 1. Technologies and strategies to be implemented in Vicat.

Technology	Partners involved
Innovative crusher	METSO
Weighing systems equipped with sensors implemented on strategic conveyors belts	ARCO
Preventive maintenance strategy with a BIM MODEL	APP
Build an H&S simulation model with energy consumption indicators	CHALMERS and ROCTIM
Treatment automation and production control	MAESTRO
AI algorithms and MetaQuarry	SIGMA and UPM-AI
Social acceptance strategy	ZABALA

2.1 Metso's Innovative Crusher

Metso is currently developing an electric mobile crusher. The main innovation is the replacement of a diesel engine with an electric motor. The operating principle does not change. Deconstruction materials are loaded into a hopper equipped on the machine. An impact crusher makes it possible to reduce their particle size according to demand. A conveyor belt allows the crushed materials to be evacuated while an overband allows the metal waste separated from the recycled materials to be evacuated.

Today we use a thermal crusher. Changing energy will allow us to reduce fossil energy consumption and therefore reduce our CO2 emissions. This will also reduce noise emissions from the heat engine, to reduce nuisance for our close neighbors.

To date, Metso has planned to test its innovative mobile crusher in Finland in spring 2024. The test at our site is planned for the third quarter of the same year.

Figure 2: METSO innovative mobile crusher.

2.2 Arco's weighting system

ARCO ELEC has installed two weighting systems on two conveyor belts: the ones carrying 4/14 and 11/22 types of aggregates. Granulats Vicat did not have sensors on those conveyors which means that materials produced in 4/14 and 11/22 had to be calculated and roughly estimated from the total volume of production and entry data. The new weighting systems enable in real-time information of how much is produced. 4/14 and 11/22 types of aggregates are used in concrete manufacturing.

The weighting system can uphold up to 20 000 t/h, it has a speed sensor with high precision and communicates with a PC by Ethernet.

Now what is needed is more information on how to effectively exploit those data to send them digitally since the pilot writes them down manually. The first solution would be to connect ARCO system to Vicat existing SCADA.

Figure 3: Arco's weighting system.

2.3 BIM Model

Discussions are being held with APP to finalize the 3D BIM model that will allow the team on site to manage predictive maintenance and thus detect any failure or breakdown. The solution which best fitted the quarry's need is an app: the pilot will have a tour of the site to do, with mandatory control stops. As an app on smartphone or tablet is easier to use, it will be possible to directly report any future failure or scheduled maintenance on the app to prevent any equipment from failing.

On the app, they will report current state of the equipment and it will automatically be added to the model and by clicking on an equipment it will be possible to get its state of progress, planned maintenance and failure detection.

This will allow us to anticipate breakdowns, which will make it easier for us to predict and organize maintenance (in particular the mobilization of labour as well as the duration of downtime of the installation) and thus increase the productivity of the site.

Figure 4. Maintenance tool model.

For the moment, anticipation of maintenance on the Fenouillet site is basic. The installation pilot carries out a tour of the production tool, then transmits its report to the operations manager who integrates the actions to be planned into a maintenance action plan.

To develop this technology, we analyzed all the equipment to be checked as well as the different specific points of each (such as for example, the condition of the screen grids or the wear of the conveyor belt rollers).

The first draft of a solution that will be computed on the app was made and sent to APP: with predictive maintenance targets, a plan of a tour duty around the site on which the pilot will have mandatory checkup instructions. They will have to inspect possible failures, cracks, leakage, and other types of malfunctions. Considering previous incidents or breakdowns, it was possible to evaluate the equipment at risks and its outcome on overall production.

Figure 5. Overview of the BIM platform.

2.4 Treatment automation and production control

To work with MAESTRO on the optimization of the treatment process, the first step was to list the different existing sensors to identify what could be added.

The main idea was to set up a weighing system on the conveyor belt of crushed 0/20 to obtain information on production flow rates as well as cameras upstream and downstream of the crusher to measure the proper functioning of this one. This will allow the installation driver to optimize the crusher setting to have the most regular aggregate possible.

Table 2. List of present sensors on the treatment plant.

Sensors	Position
amper outlet	chain extractor AL3, screens C3, C2, C1, crusher K1
vibration sensor	
pressure sensor	screen C3, flocculator, washing tank CV3, cyclone cy2 and cy1
low level sensor	
high level and very high-level sensor	belt TR2BIS TR3BIS TR5 TR6 TC3BIS
jam probe sensor	extractor AL3, conveyor T7 T8 T9 T11, belt T1 TC2 TC3 crusher K2
density measurement	decanter feed box
analogue prob	chain hopper TR3, easement pump 5.5, 2 flocculators, recycled water tank, crusher hopper TR2, crusher K1
break sensor	AL3
"End of race" sensor	screening trolley C3
position sensor	rotating walkaway 1.1
vein sensor	washing pump
rotation control	conveyor T7 T8 T9 T10 T11 belt T1 TR2 TR2BIS TR3 TR3BIS TR4 TR5 TR6 TC1 TC2 TC3 TC3BIS
weighting system	conveyor T7 T9 belt T1 TR2

The references in the table above refer to the synoptic in Annex 1.

2.5 AI algorithm and MetaQuarry

Regarding WP4 tasks with SIGMA and UPM-AI, Vicat assisted SIGMA and UPM-AI in conducting noise measures on site and camera testing of the stockpiles from different angles to question which position would suit best the future cameras for stockpile calculations. Vicat's team provided SIGMA and UPM-AI with aerials pictures and videos of the stockpiles and it was mentioned the collection of satellite images of the site stockpiles from the European Space Agency (ESA). Discussions are being held on the accuracy of the future cameras' placement and their connection to a computer to get real time footage.

The team has been uploading documents of various sorts on the Metaquarry platform to feed it with more content. This service facilitates searches for specific documents, it ranges from technical data sheets of equipment, data of production or maintenance.

The screenshot displays the MetaQuarry search interface. On the left, there is a sidebar with the DEQ logo and the text 'MetaQuarry Vicat'. Below this, it describes the platform as a search engine and information retriever. A search bar in the sidebar contains the text 'MetaQuarry'. The main interface features a search input field with the query 'granulats'. Below the input field, there is a dropdown menu for selecting a testing question list. The search results indicate that a reliable answer was not found in the documents, but 33 documents were found. One document is highlighted: '2019-12 EDR Fenouillet.xls'. The document's path is shown as 'webdav > safety > Documents de Sécurité > Evaluation des risques professionnels > Archive'. The document's text includes: 'TEXT : 1er Page GRANULATS Formulaire EVALUATION DES RISQUES Réf : G-F-029 Indice : 4 Date : 03/11/2014 Date MàJ : 17/12/19 Ce document ne peut être communiqué, copié, modifié ou reproduit sans notre autorisation écrite préalable. EVALUATION DES RISQUES Domaine d'application : L'ensemble des sites et locaux de la Branche Granulats. Objet : Ce'. A 'Download' button is visible next to the document title.

Figure 6. Metaquarry search results.

2.6 Simulation model for environment and safety indicators

Chalmers and Roctim teams have been setting and updating an online platform, Plantsmith. Data from 2019 has been gathered and analysed to trace back energy consumption and production. New data is being exchanged and the possibility of collecting data directly through Vicat's SCADA system has been introduced.

Figure 7. Plantsmith models of Fenouillet's quarry from 2019.

3 Results

Today, the new sensors installed by ARCO allow us to effectively report to the site operations manager daily production of each type of aggregate. The KPIs were initially about hourly production and energy consumption. Thanks to the new weighting systems we can report those data.

APP solution ignited this process that we are putting in form and working on, their work will highly benefit us as it will allow us to construct our maintenance and production planning.

We are still actively collaborating with the other partners to improve data collection and technology deployment.

4 Future

In the future, it is expected to have SIGMA cameras installed on site. Those will allow us to get stockpile information in real time and adjust production accordingly.

Abaut is supposed to install another camera that will detect any possible contaminant in the coming materials. It will be placed for example at the front of our site, and we will determine how dirty those materials are and then adjust water usage, energy consumption since it depends on the quality of the materials. To do so, Vicat will send on the 30th of November some pictures and videos of the front of the site as samples, in early 2024 ABAUT will send a professional 360° camera to continue sampling.

We are actively discussing with MAESTRO to install weighting systems to track quality of the crushed materials. To do so, it is important first to connect MAESTRO to Vicat's SCADA before being able to get valuable data.

Regarding public acceptance, Granulats Vicat plans on organizing open gates of the quarry to neighbouring businesses, public and institutions. This would be the occasion to communicate on the project and let the public know about the steps that are being taken to improve on materials quality, safety, and environmental impact.

The test of Metso's electric mobile crusher on our site, which will be carried out in September or October 2024, will allow us to study the percentage reduction in the environmental impacts of our recycling activity.

5 Conclusion

Vicat is now waiting for our IT Team to connect our data to the data lake as well as getting ARCO and MAESTRO data on the cloud. Our IT Team and our SCADA supplier are keys to accessing data easily and transfer them to our partners or the data lake.

The upcoming solutions are very promising, and we are looking forward to developing them.

We get a wider view of the project.

A lot of processes are still in discussion, but more technologies are expected on our site, and we are working on the best cases of use of the technologies in the scope of the project as well as our social acceptance strategy.

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